

CONCEPTUAL STUDY ON EFFECTS OF MURVADI AGAD IN GARAVISHAJANYA VYADHI: A REVIEW

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18937781>

How to cite this Article: Vd. Anjum Shaikh*. (2026). CONCEPTUAL STUDY ON EFFECTS OF MURVADI AGAD IN GARAVISHAJANYA VYADHI: A REVIEW. European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research, 13(3), 503–506. This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

Article Received on 15/02/2026

Article Revised on 05/03/2026

Article Published on 10/03/2026

ABSTRACT

Agadtantra is a branch of Ashtang Ayurveda in which there are number of Agad Yoga. Vishaghna property of these Yogas are due to special characteristic feature of their individual ingredient i.e. its Rasa (taste), Virya (potency), Vipaka, Guna and Prabhava karya. Murvadi Agad is one of them which is explained by Acharya Vagbhata in Ashtang Sangraha Uttarasthana and Ashtang Hriday Uttarasthana. It is indicated in the treatment of Agnimandya due to Garavisha. It is considered as one of the form of *Kritrim Visha* (Artificial poison), which is formed by the combination of two or more poisonous or nonpoisonous drugs. *Garavisha Lakshane* such as *Pandu, Alpagni, Durbalatha, Vayu Pratiloma, Shopha*, etc. are Garavishajanya Vyadhi. *Moorva, Amrita, Nata, Kana, Patola, Chavya, Chitraka, Vacha, Musta, Vidanga* are the contents of Murvadi Agad. In this paper, a conceptual study is proposed to evaluate the effect of *Murvadi Agad* in Garavishajanya Vyadhi.

KEYWORDS: Vishaghna, Agad, Garavisha, Vyadhi.

INTRODUCTION

Agadtantra is a branch of science which deals with study of Visha Chikitsa (treatment of poison), that Visha may Jangam Visha, Sthavar Visha or Kritrim Visha and Chikitsa (treatment) is well described by ancient Acharya. Garavisha is a Kritrim Visha, it is one of form of Samyogaj Visha, as it forms in body due to unhealthy diet or due to combination of incompatible food items.^[1] Acharya Vagbhata mentioned in Ashtang Hriday that toxic effects of Viruddhaahara (incompatible food) are same as Garavisha.^[2] Acharya Vagbhata explained the importance of Murvadi Churna in the management of Garavisha.^[3]

➤ AIMS

To study medicinal uses of *Murvadi Agad* in *Garavishajanya Vyadhi*.

➤ OBJECTIVES

To evaluate and discuss the *Ayurveda* properties of *Murvadi Agad* and its mode of Action on *Garavishajanya Vyadhi*.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

- The study on Murvadi Agad and Garavishajanya Vyadhi was done with the help of Ayurveda Samhita specially *Ashtang Sangraha and Ashtang Hriday*.
- Then conceptualize and summarized the data of different *Samhita*.
- Journals has also been referred to review of material of concept topic

CONCEPTUAL STUDY

Diseases of *Garavisha* According to Acharya Vagbhata are *Pandu* (Anemia), *Alpagni, Ardita, Vata Pratiloma, Udara, Daurbalya, Shandhya, Andhya, Visarpa, Udara, Visphota, Unmada, Bhagandara, Aamvisha, Kushtha, Shotha, Amlapitta, Jwara*, etc.^[4]

Garavisha

Garavisha is a *Samyogaj Visha* which exerts toxic effects after interval of time and it does not kill patient instantly. It produces many diseases after long time. *Garavisha* is a *Kalantar Vipaki*, it means it does not get digested early. It remains in body for long time and do not eliminate. It further produces clinical features.^[5]

Mode of Action of Garavishajanya Vyadhi

रोगः सर्वे अपि मंदाग्रौ

Mandagni is the root causes to start the pathology of diseases.^[6]

Prolonged and frequent intake of *Viruddhaahara* (incompatible diet), food additives, and soft drinks becomes harmful to body as these are toxic and forms of Garavisha.

When it is ingested, it does not get digested properly. It remains in body and do not eliminate from the body.

This *Visha* are antagonist to *Deha Dhatu* (Body Tissue), hence, it interrupts the normal functioning of *Dhatu* and produces clinical features.

Further it develops into diseases i.e. *Garavishajanya Vyadhi*.

Diseases of *Garavisha* According to *Acharya Vagbhata* are *Pandu* (Anemia), *Alpagni*, *Ardita*, *Vata Pratiloma*,

Udara, *Daurbalya*, *Shandhya*, *Andhya*, *Visarpa*, *Udara*, *Visphota*, *Unmada*, *Bhagandara*, *Aamvisha*, *Kushtha*, *Shotha*, *Amlapitta*, *Jwara*, etc.

As previously said, all diseases takes form due to *Agnimandya*. If we treat *Agnimandya* with help of *Murvadi Agad*, we can successfully cure the disease by eradicating its root cause, i.e. *Mandagni*.

MURVADI AGAD

Murvadi Agad is explained By *Acharya Vagbhata* in *Ashtang Sangraha* as the treatment of *Agnimandya* due to *Garavisha*.^[7]

Ingredients

Moorva, *Amrita*, *Tagara*, *Pippali*, *Patola*, *Chavya*, *Chitraka*, *Vacha*, *Musta* and *Vidanga*
These *Churna* should be taken with *Anupana* like *Takra*, *Koshna Jala*, *Mastu*, or *Amla Rasa dravya*.^[8]

Method of preparation

All the ingredients are taken in equal quantity. They are pounded separately, sieved and mixed homogenously.

Dose: 1 Karsha (12g)^[9]

Ingredients	Botanical name	Rasa	Guna	Veerya	Vipaka	Doshagnata
Moorva ^[10]	<i>Marsdenia tenacissima</i>	Tikta Kashaya	Guru Ruksha	Ushna	Katu	Kapha Vatahara
Guduchi ^[11]	<i>Tinospora cordifolia</i>	Tikta Kashaya	Guru Snigdha	Ushna	Madhura	Tridoshaghna
Tagara ^[12]	<i>Valeriana wallichii</i>	Tikta Katu Kashaya	Laghu Snigdha	Ushna	Katu	Kapha vataghna
Pippali ^[13]	<i>Piper longum</i>	Katu	Laghu Snigdha	Ushna	Madhura	Vata Kaphaghna
Patola ^[14]	<i>Tricosanthes dioica</i>	Tikta Katu	Laghu Ruksha	Ushna	Katu	Kapha Pittaghna
Chavya ^[15]	<i>Piper chaba</i>	Katu	Laghu Ruksha	Ushna	Katu	Kapha Vata Shamaka
Chitraka ^[16]	<i>Plumbago zeylanica</i>	Katu	Laghu, Ruksha	Ushna	Katu	Kapha Vatahara
Vacha ^[17]	<i>Acorus calamus</i>	Katu Tikta	Laghu Tikshna	Ushna	Katu	Kapha Vatahara
Musta ^[18]	<i>Cyprus Rotundus</i>	Tikta Katu Kashaya	Laghu Ruksha	Sheeta	Katu	Kaphapittaghna
Vidanga ^[19]	<i>Embelia ribes</i>	Katu Kashaya	Laghu Ruksha	Ushna	Katu	Kaphavataghna

Pharmacological Action of ingredients of *Murvadi Agad* according to *Ayurveda*

Drug	Karma
Moorva ^[10]	Jwarhara, Premehahara, Kushthaghna, Chardhighna
Guduchi ^[11]	Medhya, Rasayana, Deepaniya, Grahi, Medohara, Kandughna, Jwarhara, Daha prashamana
Tagara ^[12]	Vishaghna, Bhootha Apasmara Nashaka
Pippali ^[13]	Deepaniya, Vrishya, Rasayana, Kushthaghna, Shulahara
Patola ^[14]	Vrshya, Varnya, Deepana
Chavya ^[15]	Deepaniya, Pachana, Shwasaghna, Kasaghna
Chitraka ^[16]	Deepaniya, Pachaniya, Grahi
Vacha ^[17]	Legkhaniya, Medhya
Musta ^[18]	Deepaniya, Pachaniya, Grahi, Lekhana
Vidanga ^[19]	Krimighna, Deepaniya, Kushthaghna

Anupana	Doshagnata	Properties
Koshna Jala (Hot water)	Kapha Vata	Removes Meda (fat) and Ama Deepana (stimulates digestive fire), Basti Shodhana (cleanses urinary bladder), alleviate Shwasa (dyspnea), Kasa (cough), Jwara (fever) and is always wholesome. ^[4]
Takra (Butter milk)	Kapha Vata	Having Kashaya Amla rasa (astringent and sour taste) Deepana (stimulates digestive fire), alleviates Shopha (swelling), Udara (ascites), Arsha (piles), Grahani (irritable bowel syndrome), Mutra Graha (incontinence of urine), Aruchi (tastelessness), Pleeha (splenomegaly), Ghrita Vyapad (complication due to ghee intake), Pandu (anemia). ^[5]
Mastu(Whey)	Kapha Vata	Amla-Kashaya-Madhura rasa (sour, astringent and sweet taste), Laghu (light), removes Trishna (thirst) and Klama (exhaustion), Sroto Vishodhana (cleanses channels), prahladana (pleasing), Preenana (satiating), quickly breaks faeces down, strengthens the body quickly.
Amla rasa Dravya (substance having sour taste)	Vata	Causes agni Deepana, Hridya (conductive to heart), Pachana (digestive), Rochana (appetizer), having Ushna Veerya (hot potency), Preenana (satiating), Kledana (slimy), Laghu (light), causes aggravation of Kapha and pitta, Moodha Vatanulomana (makes inactive Vata move downwards). ^[7]

Probable Mode of action of Murvadi Agad on Garavishajanya Vyadhi

In absence of proper digestion, improper formation of Rasa Dhatu takes place. Due to this further Uttarottara Dhatu Poshana hampers i.e., formation Rakta from Rasa, Mansa from Rakta, Meda from Mansa and so on. As Dhatu Poshana gets hampers, Vikruti takes place in corresponding Dhatu, it leads into formation Vyadhi. So if there chronic consumption of incompatible food, it leads into formation of Garavisha.

सात्म्यतो अल्पतया वापि दिप्तीग्निस्तरुणस्य च
स्निग्धव्यायामबलीना विरुद्धम वितथम भवेत्

च. सू. (२६/१०६)

Acharya Charaka mentioned that incompatible diet become affectless in person who have strong digestive power (Deepatagni).^[20]

Hence to treat Garavishajanya Vyadhi, we have to strengthen one's Jatharagni strength.

DISCUSSION

In Murvadi Agad, Guduchi, Pippali, Chavya, Patola, Chitraka, Musta and Vidanga are Deepaniya Dravya. This Dravya can increase digestive fire. Chavya, Chitraka, Musta are Pachaniya Dravya, these Dravya can digest whatever heavy food that will be. Due to Deepana and Pachana action, food gets properly digested and there will proper formation of Ahar Rasa. From Aahara Rasa, Rasa Dhatu forms in Prakrit Condition and Uttarottara Dhatu Poshana will be. Therefore Diseases like Ajirna, Pandu, Visarpa, Kushtha, Amlapitta, Aamosha, and Jwara can be treated with Murvadi Agad

Murva, Pippali and Vidanga are Kushthagha Dravya. Tagara having Vishagha property helps to reduce the artificial poison. Mastu which is Sara (laxative) and

Srotoshodhak (clears the metabolic pathways), helps the evacuation of flatus. The Anupana mentioned for Murvadi churna all are having Deepana property that help to manage the Agnimandya caused due to Garavisha. Takra is indicated in Garavisha and all Agnimandya Vikara like Grahani, Arsha and Udara. Koshna Jala (hot water) which is Ama Pachana helps for proper digestion and absorption. The Amla Dravya having Deepana and Pachana property and are also good appetizers.

CONCLUSION

According to action of Murvadi Agad when taken with proper Anupana and due to its medicinal properties, *Garavishajanya Vyadhi* can be treated successfully by use of Murvadi Agad. Table mentioned above clearly shows that *Murvadi Agad* with its ingredients have excellent property to combat with Agnimandya. It reestablish the interrupted *Rasa Dhatu Vikruti* by *strengthening Jatharagni*, by *increasing digestive fire*. So that other *Dhatu Forms* by *Uttarottara Dhatu Poshana*. However, further clinical study is required to assess the therapeutic effects of Murvadi Agad in Garavishajanya Vyadhi.

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